

Consumer's Perception Towards Organic Food Products – A Systematic Review Of Literature

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Abstract:

Organic marketing, as a whole, is a marketing system. In the current context, the organic food market in India is extremely challenging. Recently, it has been observed that Indian consumers are becoming increasingly interested in healthy and high-quality food with high nutritional value, environmental concerns, and food safety. A person who has a favorable attitude toward an organic food product is more likely to purchase it, making consumer attitudes research critical for marketers. Consumers' food consumption habits are changing around the world, and they now prefer food that is free of synthetic chemicals, fertilizers, and pesticides, i.e., they prefer organic food that is not only healthy but also environmentally friendly. Organic products are less popular among consumers due to farmers' lower productivity of organic produce, which results in high market prices for organic food. There is a need to raise public awareness about the benefits of organic food products and promote their use, while the primary need is to encourage farmers to choose organic farming. A study of consumer perceptions of organic food could help the emerging organic food industry in India and around the world. The review of related literature in the area of organic food market and consumer perception studied yielded numerous insights for the study. It has also guided the design of the current study. A number of researchers have identified the global and Indian demand for organic food products. In addition, various factors influencing consumer perception of organic food products have been identified. Some studies have also been conducted to determine consumer preferences, knowledge, and satisfaction with organic food products. After reviewing several studies and identifying the gap, the investigator felt compelled to conduct the current investigation.

Keywords: Organic food products, organic food market, Consumer perception, consumer attitude, nutritional value, organic farming

Introduction:

The global organic food market has expanded significantly in recent years, and over the past ten years, it has attracted a lot of media attention. Sales of organic goods are rising by more than \$5 billion annually, indicating that demand for them is still high globally (Willer and Yussefi Menzler, 2002). The organic food market in India has expanded at a rate of 20–22% annually over the past few years. The nation has the capacity to overtake other nations as the top producer of organic food. In India, there are currently over 15,000 certified organic farms, and this number is rising quickly. In addition, many small farmers cultivate organic food using organic methods (Menon, 2009). Consumer demand will have a significant impact on the future of organic agriculture. Since market dynamics are constantly changing, it is crucial to understand holistic and green marketing from the perspective of the consumer. Understanding consumers' long-term attitudes toward organically produced foods and how consumption can be encouraged is crucial from a marketing

perspective. Product development and marketing tactics are influenced by consumer attitudes, responses, and beliefs. Depending on where you are in the world, this might be different. As a result, it is crucial to comprehend consumer attitudes toward organically grown products in India as well as the driving forces behind their behavior. Organic farming is a method of farming that has been used by farmers since antiquity and is devoid of artificial fertilizers, pesticides, growth promoters, and additives to livestock feed. The FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission (2007) defined organic agriculture as an integrated production management system that fosters and enhances the health of the agro-ecosystem, including biodiversity, biological cycles, and soil biological activity. It places a focus on using natural inputs (like minerals and products derived from plants) and avoiding synthetic pesticides and fertilizers. In contrast to conventional farming methods, organic agriculture adheres to the principle of sustainability by using natural inputs, environmentally friendly practices like crop

rotation, mulching, and intercropping, as well as enhancements to soil fertility and structure. Nowadays, almost every nation on earth engages in organic farming, which is growing in popularity. The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) claims that both at the national and international levels, the rapidly evolving trend away from chemical-based agriculture toward organic and environmentally friendly farming systems is of great concern. According to the most recent survey, India has 6,50,000 organic producers and 5.2 million hectares of organic land. India has the highest proportion of organic producers worldwide. Food that has been grown using an organic farming method without the use of pesticides or synthetic fertilizers is known as organic food. Demand for organic food is rising as a result of consumers' increased awareness of health risks, which is promoting this shift toward organic production. Consumption of organic food products is rising overall among consumers. There is no universal definition of "organic," as different nations have different requirements for products to be certified as such. According to research, consumers understand what "organic" means in general (e.g., Bourn and Prescott, 2002; FAO, 1999; Klosky and Tourte, 1998; Goldman and Hylton, 1972). According to Indian consumers, organic produce or products are those that are produced and processed using environmentally friendly methods, non-chemically treated, fresh or minimally processed, free of pesticides, without genetically modified organisms, and have organic certificates. As more people desire to eat organic food and have a favorable opinion of organic food products, the market for organic products is growing. Positive attitudes and motivating factors toward organic food products will play a significant role in determining the future of organic agriculture. A number of studies have been carried out to look into the problem in the context of overall consumer behavior and attitudes toward organic food (Gracia and de Magistris, 2007; Grankvist and Biel, 2001; Zanolli and Nasppetti, 2002; Chen, 2007; Harper and Makatouni, 2002; Padel and Foster, 2005). Researchers Chen (2007), Gracia and de Magistris (2007), Grankvist and Biel (2001), and Gracia and de Magistris (2007) found that Indians have a favorable view of organic food products (1991) This is

supported by Pirjo Honkanen, Bas Verplanken, and Svein Ottar Olsen (2006) as well as Victoria Kulikovski and Manjola Agolli (2010) who found that favorable attitudes toward the purchase of organic food will be generated.

Research Design

The demand for organic food products is rising quickly, but there has always been global concern about how people perceive buying and consuming organic products. To understand and meet the demand for organic food products, producers (farmers) and retailers (business owners) must have a thorough understanding of consumer perceptions and attitudes toward buying those products. Numerous studies on organic products have been conducted over the past few years; however, the main objective of the current study is to provide a thorough overview of consumer perceptions of organic food products.

Major objectives of the present study:

Based on the literature review, the specific objectives of the present study are as follows:

1. To provide updated and efficient review of organic market and organic food (World and Indian scenario)
2. To study various research aspect widespread in the ground of consumer perceptions of organic food products through academic research papers.

Data source and methodology:

Information was gathered from various research articles published in referred journals as well as in electronic databases related to the organic market in the global and Indian contexts in order to review the extensive literature. The perceptions of consumers toward organic food products were later the subject of a thorough review of the literature. The journals offer the excellent work of numerous scholars from around the world, which ultimately aids in conducting their work in an ideal manner. Additionally, an effort was made to track down references cited in a number of reports and published articles about organic food products. The majority of the information was gathered from both primary and secondary sources.

Findings from the literature

Overview of Organic Market and Organic Food (World and Indian Scenario)

Organic food sales have been growing annually on a global scale; in 2010, they grew

by 23%. The organic food market was valued at 59.1 billion US dollars. The largest amount of land was purchased for organic apple production in 2001 in the United States (17272 acres). Of all the countries in Europe, Italy, Germany, France, Switzerland, and Austria produce the most organic fruits (Yadav et al, 2010). The market for organic products is expanding quickly, according to the National Program on Organic Production 2012 report, reaching 47% in the EU, 28% in the USA, and 28% in Canada. Singapore and Italy's markets are also growing at a healthy rate. Although a sizeable portion of this demand is met by domestic producers in these countries, there is still a sizable demand for many other commodities in addition to sizable quantities of the ones that are already in supply. This supply-demand imbalance will present opportunities for developing countries like India to look into. In both Europe and the US, products made from organic food are frequently used. Asia, which is not far behind, has India as a major player. Organic food is not a novel concept for Indian farmers. There is not much domestic consumption going on, despite the fact that India is one of the top 10 countries in the world for the number of farmers who practice organic farming (Balaji and Injodey, 2017). There has been a noticeable rise in the demand for and consumption of organic food in both developed and developing countries. This is true because consumers are becoming more and more concerned about their health. The perception and understanding of organic food production in Malaysia is based primarily on the avoidance of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, despite organic food accounting for a relatively small portion of the food market, organic food has seen rapid growth, which has attracted the attention of consumers, businesses, as well as researchers. The organic food industry in Malaysia is facing a number of challenges. Although demand for organic food is rising in Malaysia, there is not enough local production of organic goods to meet this demand (Somasundram et al., 2014). The organic food industry in India is only now beginning to grow. Due to rising disposable income and increased health awareness, there is a greater domestic demand for organic food. Selling organic goods offers a significant premium to wealthy, health-conscious domestic consumers as well as

export markets (Manaloor et al., 2016). The organic food industry has experienced unexpected growth in recent years. The amount of certified organic agricultural land worldwide, at 43.16 million hectares, is still only about 1%. When 11 million hectares of organic farming were recorded in 1999, this is almost four times that amount of land (Lernoud and Willer 2016). Even though consumption in developed countries is rising, the domestic demand in developing nations continues to be a problem for the organic food industry. Many things, it has been suggested, may have prevented the domestic growth of organic foods in developing countries. High cost, accessibility, brand trust, awareness of organic foods, etc. were a few of them (Sangkumchaliang and Huang 2012).

Consumer Attitude and Perceptions towards Organic Food Products

The way that consumers eat is rapidly changing in the modern world. The organic niche market is about to explode. Since a few years ago, there has been an increase in the production of organic products, which has had a significant impact on the economy. Because organic food is healthier and less likely to contain chemicals than conventional food, many people have begun to favor it over conventional food. This type of shopping behavior is crucial in determining consumer attitudes and perceptions toward buying organic food. Additionally, a thorough review of earlier studies has allowed for the identification of the problems, issues, and key causes.

Gender, age, income, education level, and whether or not there are children in the home all play a major role in how people approach buying organic food (Magnusson et al., 2001; Wier et al., 2003) The main factors driving consumer preference for organic food were identified by Hughner et al. in 2007. Concerns about nutrition and health, superior taste, environmental protection, food safety, distrust of conventional foods, concern for animal welfare, support for the local economy, freshness, curiosity, or because they are deemed trendy are the main drivers. People eat this kind of food for a variety of reasons, but most of them are connected to animal welfare and environmental friendliness, according to Chiciudean et al. (2012). Results show that age and gender are important influencing factors for consumers. The taste and quality

of organic food are primarily praised. Price and the fashionable aspect of being "organic" have an impact on women as well. People of different ages exhibit significant differences when it comes to promotions, personal recommendations, and advertising. Adults are influenced by promotions, whereas children are more influenced by advertising than any other age group. Shafie and Rennie (2012) studied consumer perceptions of organic food and discovered that sensory factors like nutritive value, taste, freshness, and appearance, as well as concerns about food safety, human health, and the environment, have an impact on consumer preferences for organic food. Organic food consumption continues to be stifled by premium prices. Understanding the factors that are driving people to consume more organic food, such as motivation, is essential to realizing how the market for organic food can grow. The perceptions of consumers regarding the consumption of organic food are influenced by five variables: food safety, cost, environmental friendliness, nutrition, and sensory qualities. As a result of environmental and health concerns, food consumption patterns are constantly changing. According to Mukul et al. in 2013, the demand for food grown organically is growing everywhere in the world. Six important factors were found by Mehra and Ratna (2014) to have an impact on people's attitudes toward organic food. They included attitudes toward eating organic food, health awareness, product information, product value, accessibility, and trust. The study's findings indicated that women and younger consumers had a favorable attitude toward organic food and thought eating it was a healthier option. When choosing nutrient-dense foods, they were eager to compare labels and obtain product information. Women thought eating organic food was a healthier choice. In 2014, Sharma and Bali came to the conclusion that consumers are well aware of the benefits of organic food for their health and that these products are safe for them to purchase because they don't contain any chemicals. Urban consumers are more knowledgeable about organic food options. The consumer thinks that eating organic food contributes to maintaining an active lifestyle and lowering stress levels. This study also discovered that respondents are willing to pay even higher prices when it

comes to health benefits. According to Sivathanu, a different researcher, consumers prefer to purchase organic food items because they believe these items to be safe, wholesome, and environmentally friendly. Labels, health concerns, environmental concerns, brand advertising, brand safety, accessibility, affordability, freshness, and store location were identified by Pandurangarao et al. (2017) as the top ten factors influencing consumers to purchase organic food. Out of these, the most important determining factors are safety, the environment, and health.

Research in Organic Food an Overview:

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accounting for a relatively small portion of the food market, organic food has seen rapid growth, which has attracted the attention of consumers, businesses, as well as researchers. The organic food industry in Malaysia is facing a number of challenges. Although demand for organic food is rising in Malaysia, there is not enough local production of organic goods to meet this demand (Somasundram et al., 2014). The organic food industry in India is only now beginning to grow. Due to rising disposable income and increased health awareness, there is a greater domestic demand for organic food. Selling organic goods offers a significant premium to wealthy, health-conscious domestic consumers as well as export markets (Manaloor et al., 2016). The organic food industry has experienced unexpected growth in recent years. The amount of certified organic agricultural land worldwide, at 43.16 million hectares, is still only about 1%. When 11 million hectares of organic farming were recorded in 1999, this is almost four times that amount of land (Lernoud and Willer 2016). Even though consumption in developed countries is rising, the domestic demand in developing nations continues to be a problem for the organic food industry. Many things, it has been suggested, may have prevented the domestic growth of organic foods in developing countries. High cost, accessibility, brand trust, awareness of organic foods, etc. were a few of them (Sangkumchaliang and Huang 2012). Accordingly, our objectives in this study have been to:

Determine the interrelationships between the chosen motivation and attitude constructs separately and the influences of demographics and time on the constructs
Study the influence of these constructs on behavioral related characteristics like regular and occasional purchase of organic food categories

Conclusion and further recommendations

This study sought to understand how Indian consumers felt about eating organic food. Understanding consumer behavior and decision-making towards organically grown products, it was discovered that consumer attitudes and preferences toward buying organic products were primarily influenced by concerns about their health, safety, taste, and environment. The availability of the

market can affect consumers' preferences and decisions for buying organic food products, according to the study review. The demand for food grown organically will therefore increase in the future, indicating that it is imperative for producers, traders, consumers, and the government to concentrate on this niche market. Compared to non-innovators, those who value health, nutrition, taste, and the need to care for the sick place a higher value on these factors. Between frequent and infrequent buyers, as well as between innovators and non-innovators, the importance attached to the conviction about the utility of organic food, reputation, and certification is roughly at the same level, indicating that these requirements are more universal in nature. A statistically significant and favorable correlation exists between the number of categories purchased by both frequent and infrequent customers and health motivation. Number of categories bought occasionally is also correlated with conviction about utility attitude, whereas number of categories bought regularly is also correlated with motivations of nutrition, taste, and the need to care for sick people. For both types of buyers, health and nutrition are the main driving forces. Regular buyers place more importance on taste motivation, while occasional buyers place more emphasis on curiosity.

References:

1. Ajzen, I. Aryal et al. Theory of planned behavior Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes 1991, 50:179-211. (2009)
2. Asli Ucar and Ayse Ozfer Ozcelik. in their article entitled "University Student Attitudes Toward Organic Foods" found out that the students' 2009
3. Baker S, Thompson KE, Engelken J. mapping the values driving organic food choice. European, 2004
4. Blackwell, R. D., Miniard, P. W., & Engel, J. F. Consumer Behavior (10 ed.): Thomson South-Western, 2006
5. Bourn, D. and Prescott, J. A comparison of the nutritional value, sensory qualities and food safety of organically and conventionally produced foods. Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition. 2002, 42(1): 1-34
6. Briz, T. & Ward, R.W. "Consumer awareness of organic products in Spain: an application of multinomial logit models", Food Policy, Vol. 34 (3), 2009, pp. 295-304
7. Budi Suprpto and Tony Wijaya in their research work entitled "Model of Consumer's Buying Intention towards Organic Food: A Study among Mothers in Indonesian" 201211

8. Chen, M.F. Consumer attitudes and purchase intentions in relation to organic foods in Taiwan: Moderating effects of food-related personality traits. *Food Quality and Preference*, Vol. 18, 2007, pp. (1008-1021), ISSN: 0950-3293
9. Balaji V, Injodey JI. Organic Food Products: A Study on Perceptions of Indian Consumers. *Indian Journal of Marketing*. 2017, 47(1).
10. Chiciudean D, Funar S, Arion F, Chirla G, Man A. The Factors of Influence over the Consumer Buying Behaviour for Organic Food. *Bulletin UASVM Horticulture*. 2017; 69 (2):68-71.
11. FAO, WHO. Codex Alimentarius: organically produced food. Third edition. 2007, Retrieved from: <http://www.codexalimentarius.org/standards/the-matic-compilations/en/>
12. Hughner R, McDonagh S, Prothero ACJ, Shultz II Stanton J. Who are organic food consumers? A compilation and review of why people purchase organic food. *Journal of consumer behavior*. 2007; 6:1-17.
13. Laheri VK, Arya PK. A Study on Consumer Decision towards Purchase of Organic Food Products: A Case Study of Delhi. *Indian Journal of Commerce & Management Studies*. 2015; 6(2):84-87.
14. Lernoud J, Willer H. *The World of Organic Agriculture. Statistics and Emerging Trends 2016*. Bonn: Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, and IFOAM - Organics International, 2016.
15. Magnusson M, Arvola A, Koivisto Hursti U, Aberg L, Sjoden P. Attitudes towards organic foods among Swedish consumers. *British Food Journal*. 2001; 103(3):209-26.
16. Manaloor V, Srivastava D, Islam S. Growth of Organic Food Industry in India. *AGROFOR International Journal*. 2016; 1(2):69-76.
17. Mehra S, Ratna PA. Attitude and behavior of consumers towards organic food: an exploratory study in India. *International Journal of Business Excellence*. 2014; 7(6):677-696.
18. Mukul AZA, Afrin S, Hassan M. Factor's affecting consumers' perceptions about organic food and their prevalence in Bangladeshi organic preference. *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*. 2013; 1:112-118.
19. National Program for Organic production Report, 2012.
20. Pandurangarao D, Chiranjeevi K, Rao DS. Factors Affecting Consumers to Buy Organic Food Products in Hyderabad and Secuderabad. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*. 6(3), 24-30.
21. Paul J, Rana J. Consumer behavior and purchase intention for organic food. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*. 2012; 29:412-422.
22. Somasundram C, Razali Z, Santhirasegaram V. A Review on Organic Food Production in Malaysia. *Horticulture*. 2016; 2(12):1-5
23. Sangkumchalianga P, Huang WC. Consumers Perceptions and Attitudes of Organic Food Products in Northern Thailand. *International Food and Agribusiness Management Review*. 2012; 15(1):87-102.
24. Shafie FA, Rennie D. Consumer Perceptions towards Organic Food. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Science*. 2012; 49:360-367.
25. Sharma G, Dewan R, Bali S. Factors Influencing Consumer Buying Behavior & Awareness towards Organic Food: A Study of Chandigarh & Panchkula Consumers. *International Journal of Science and Research*. 2014; 5(2):689-696.
26. Sivathanu B. Factors Affecting Consumer Preference towards the Organic Food Purchases. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2015; 8(33):1-6. United States Department of Agriculture (USDA). Retrieved from http://agritech.tnau.ac.in/org_farm/orgfarm_introuduction.html
27. Wier M, Andersen LM, Millock K. Consumer demands for organic foods - attitudes, values and purchasing", paper presented at SOM Workshop, Environment, Information and Consumer, Frederiksdal, April, 2003.
28. Yadav AK. Organic Agriculture, Concept, Scenario, Principals and Practices. Director National Centre of Organic Farming, Ghaziabad National Centre of Organic Farming Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Govt of India, Uttar Pradesh, 2010
29. Von Alvensleben, R. and Altmann, M. 1987. Determinants of the demand for organic food in Germany. *Acta Horticulture*, 202:235-43
30. Wandel, M. and Bugge, A. 1997. Environmental concern in consumer evaluation of food quality. *Food Quality and Preference*, 8(1):19-26.
31. Willer, H., and Yussefi, M. 2004. *The World of Organic Agriculture: Statistics and Emerging Trends 2004*. *International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements*, Bonn, Germany.
32. Zanolli, R. and Naspetti, S. 2002. Consumer motivations in the purchase of organic food – A means end approach. *British Food Journal*, 104(8/9):643-653.